

Maximal Efficiencies in New Single GaAs_{1-x}Te_x-Alloy Junction Solar Cells at 300 K

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Suggested Citation

Van-Cong, H. (2024). Maximal Efficiencies in New Single GaAs_{1-x}Te_x-Alloy Junction Solar Cells at 300 K. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(1), 54-74.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(1\).04](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(1).04)

Abstract:

In single $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ [$X(x) \equiv \text{GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x$]-alloy junction solar cells at 300 K, $0 \leq x \leq 1$, by basing on the same physical model and the same treatment method, as those used in our recent work (Van Cong, 2023), we will investigate the highest (or maximal) efficiencies, $\eta_{\text{IImax. (IImax.)}}$, obtained at the open circuit voltage $V_{\text{oc}} (= V_{\text{ocI (ocII)}}$), according to highest hot reservoir temperatures $T_{\text{H}}(\text{K})$, obtained from the Carnot efficiency theorem, being proved by entropy law. Here, one first remarks that, with increasing $x=(0, 0.5,$

1), (i)- from Table 3, for the single $n^+ - p$ $X(x)$ -alloy junction solar cell and for given $r_{\text{Sn(Cd)}}$ -radius, for example, $\eta_{\text{IImax. (I)}} = 31.14\%, 31.55\%, 32.11\%$, according to $T_{\text{H}}(\text{K}) = 435.7, 438.3, 441.9$, at $V_{\text{ocI}}(\text{V}) = 1.07, 1.07, 1.06$, respectively, while, (ii)- from Table 5, for the single $p^+ - n$ $X(x)$ -alloy junction solar cell and for given $r_{\text{Cd(Sn)}}$ -radius, for example, $\eta_{\text{IImax. (II)}} = 33.04\%, 32.65\%, 32.51\%$, according to $T_{\text{H}}(\text{K}) = 448.0, 445.4, 444.5$, at $V_{\text{ocII}}(\text{V}) [> V_{\text{ocI}}(\text{V})] = 1.20, 1.19, 1.18$, respectively, suggesting that such $\eta_{\text{IImax. (IImax.)}$ -and- T_{H} variations depend on the $V_{\text{ocII}}(\text{V}) [> V_{\text{ocI}}(\text{V})] - \text{values}$. Then, as given in Table 3, for $x = 0$ and for $r_{\text{d(a)}} = r_{\text{Te(Mg)}}$, one gets: $\eta_{\text{I}} = 23.48\%$ and 29.71% at $V_{\text{oc}} = 0.98 \text{ V}$ and 1.1272 V , respectively, which can also be compared with the corresponding results, obtained for the single-junction GaAs thin-film solar cell, 22.08% and 29.71% , with relative deviations in absolute values, 6.34% and 2.1% , and given respectively by Moon et al. (2016) and Green et al. (2022). As a result, in order to obtain the highest efficiencies, the single GaAs_{1-x}Te_x-alloy junction solar cells could be chosen rather than the single crystalline GaAs-junction solar cell.

Keywords: *single GaAs_{1-x}Te_x-alloy junction solar cell; single crystalline GaAs-junction solar cell; photovoltaic conversion factor; photovoltaic conversion efficiency.*

Introduction

In single $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ GaAs_{1-x}Te_x-alloy junction solar cells at 300 K, $0 \leq x \leq 1$, by basing on the same physical model and treatment method, as used in our recent work (Van Cong, 2023), and also other works (Green, 2022; Gürbulak et al., 2021; Moon et al., 2016; Singh & Ravindra, 2012; Van Cong, 2023; Van Cong & Debiais, 1993; Van Cong et al., 1984; Yamamoto et al., 2001), we will investigate the highest (or maximal) efficiencies, $\eta_{\text{IImax. (IImax.)}}$, according to highest hot reservoir temperatures $T_{\text{H}}(\text{K})$, obtained

at the open circuit voltage: $V_{oc} = V_{ocI(ocII)}$ and from the Carnot- efficiency theorem, being proved by entropy law.

Some concluding remarks are discussed as follows.

(i)-As noted in Tables 2 and 4, the dark carrier-minority saturation current density $J_{0I(0II)}$ decreases slightly with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius for given x , and it also decreases with increasing x for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius. Then, as observed in Tables 3 and 5, at a same V_{oc} , the photovoltaic conversion factor, $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc})$, also decreases with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius for given x , and it also decreases with increasing x for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius. In other words, as discussed in Eq. (45), at a same V_{oc} , both $J_{0I(0II)}$ and $n_{I(II)}$ have the same variations for the same physical conditions. Furthermore, it should be noted in the work by Singh & Ravindra (2012) that the maximal efficiency value η_{max} . could not be obtained, since the “quality factor n ” was assumed to be equal to 1.

(ii)- Then, as observed in Tables 3 and 5, with such variations of $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc})$, the maximal values of $\eta_{I(II)}$, $\eta_{I(II)max}$, and the corresponding ones of the H-reservoir temperature, T_H , obtained at same corresponding $V_{oc} = V_{ocI(ocII)}$ -values, as marked in bold, increase slightly with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius, for a given x , and their highest values are found to be given by: $\eta_{I(II)max} = \mathbf{32.11\% (33.04\%)}$, being compared with the highly efficient single-junction GaAs thin-film solar cell on flexible substrate, 22.08 % and 29.71 %, obtained respectively by Moon et al. (2016) and Gree et al. (2022). As a result, in order to obtain the highest efficiencies, the single $\text{GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x$ -alloy junction solar cell could be chosen rather than the single crystalline GaAs-junction solar cell.

In the following, we will show that the energy-band-structure parameters, due to the effects of x -Te concentration, size impurity, temperature T and heavy doping, affect strongly the dark (or total) minority-carrier saturation current density and the photovoltaic conversion effect. Finally, some numerical results and concluding remarks will be also presented.

Energy-Band-Structure Parameters and Dark Minority-Carrier Saturation Current Density, due to the Effects of x - Te Concentration, Impurity Size, and Heavy Doping

First of all, in the single $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ $X(x)$ - alloy junction solar cells, $X(\equiv \text{CdS}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x)$, we present the effects of x -concentration, donor (acceptor) $[d(a)]$ -size, temperature T and heavy doping, affecting the energy-band-structure parameters, as those investigated in previous works (Van Cong, 2023; Gürbulak, 2021; Yamamoto, 2001).

A. Effect of x -Te Concentration

In the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ single $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ $X(x)$ - alloy junction at $T=0$ K, the energy-band-structure parameters are expressed as functions of x , are given in the following.

(i)-The unperturbed relative effective electron (hole) mass in conduction (valence) bands are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} m_c(x)/m_0 &= 0.209 \times x + 0.066 \times (1 - x), \text{ and} \\ m_v(x)/m_0 &= 0.600 \times x + 0.291 \times (1 - x), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

so that one obtains: $m_c(x=0)/m_o = m_{c(\text{GaAs})}/m_o=0.066$, $m_v(x=0)/m_o = m_{v(\text{GaAs})}/m_o=0.291$, and $m_c(x=1)/m_o = m_{c(\text{GaTe})}/m_o=0.209$, $m_v(x=1)/m_o = m_{v(\text{GaTe})}/m_o=0.600$.

(ii)-The unperturbed relative dielectric constant of the intrinsic of the single crystalline X- alloy is found to be defined by:

$$\epsilon_o(x) = 12.3 \times x + 13.13 \times (1 - x), \quad (2)$$

which gives: $\epsilon_o(x=0) = \epsilon_{\text{GaAs}}=13.13 \approx 13.1$, and $\epsilon_o(x=1) = \epsilon_{\text{GaTe}} = 12.3$.

(iii)-Finally, the unperturbed band gap at 0 K is found to be given by:

$$E_{go}(x) \text{ in eV} = 1.796 \times x + 1.52 \times (1 - x), \quad (3)$$

giving rise to: $E_{go}(x=0) = E_{g\text{GaAs}} = 1.52 \text{ eV}$, and $E_{go}(x=1) = E_{g\text{GaTe}} = 1.796 \text{ eV} \approx 1.80 \text{ eV}$.

Therefore, we can define the effective donor (acceptor)-ionization energy at $r_{d(a)} = r_{do(ao)}$ in absolute values as:

$$E_{do(ao)}(x) = \frac{13600 \times [m_c(v)(x)/m_o]}{[\epsilon_o(x)]^2} \text{ meV}, \quad (4)$$

and then, the isothermal bulk modulus, by:

$$B_{do(ao)}(x) \equiv \frac{E_{do(ao)}(x)}{(4\pi/3) \times (r_{do(ao)})^3}. \quad (5)$$

B. Effects of Impurity-Size, with a Given x

Here, the effects of $r_{d(a)}$ and x-Te concentration affect the changes in all the energy-band-structure parameters, expressed in terms of the effective relative dielectric constant $\epsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$, in the following.

At $r_{d(a)} = r_{do(ao)} = r_{As(Ga)} = 0.118 \text{ nm}$ (0.126 nm), respectively, the needed boundary conditions are found to be, for the impurity-atom volume $V = (4\pi/3) \times (r_{d(a)})^3$, $V_{do(ao)} = (4\pi/3) \times (r_{do(ao)})^3$, for the pressure p , $p_o = 0$, and for the deformation potential energy (or the strain energy) σ , $\sigma_o = 0$. Further, the two important equations (Van Cong et al., 1984), needed to determine the σ -variation $\Delta\sigma \equiv \sigma - \sigma_o = \sigma$, are defined by: $\frac{dp}{dV} = -\frac{B}{V}$ and $p = -\frac{d\sigma}{dV}$. giving: $\frac{d}{dV}(\frac{d\sigma}{dV}) = \frac{B}{V}$. Then, by an integration, one gets:

$$\left[\Delta\sigma(r_{d(a)}, x) \right]_{n(p)} = B_{do(ao)}(x) \times (V - V_{do(ao)}) \times \ln \left(\frac{V}{V_{do(ao)}} \right) = E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 \geq 0. \quad (6)$$

Furthermore, we also shown that, as $r_{d(a)} > r_{do(ao)}$ ($r_{d(a)} < r_{do(ao)}$), the compression (dilatation) gives rise to the increase (the decrease) in the energy gap $E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, and in the effective donor (acceptor)-ionization energy $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ in absolute values, obtained from the effective Bohr model, and then such the compression (dilatation) is represented respectively by: $\pm [\Delta\sigma(r_{d(a)}, x)]_{n(p)}$, respectively,

$$E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{go}(x) = E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{do(ao)}(x) = E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{\epsilon_0(x)}{\epsilon(r_{d(a)})} \right)^2 - 1 \right] = + [\Delta\sigma(r_{d(a)}, x)]_{n(p)},$$

for $r_{d(a)} \geq r_{do(ao)}$, and for $r_{d(a)} \leq r_{do(ao)}$,

$$E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{go}(x) = E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{do(ao)}(x) = E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{\epsilon_0(x)}{\epsilon(r_{d(a)})} \right)^2 - 1 \right] = - [\Delta\sigma(r_{d(a)}, x)]_{n(p)}. \quad (7)$$

Therefore, from Equations 6 and 7, one obtains the expressions for relative dielectric constant $\epsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and energy band gap $E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, as:

(i)-for $r_{d(a)} \geq r_{do(ao)}$, since $\epsilon(r_{d(a)}, x) = \frac{\epsilon_0(x)}{\sqrt{1 + \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3}} \leq \epsilon_0(x)$,

$$E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{go}(x) = E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{do(ao)}(x) = E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 \geq 0, \quad (8a)$$

according to the increase in both $E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, for a given x , and

(ii)-for $r_{d(a)} \leq r_{do(ao)}$, since $\epsilon(r_{d(a)}, x) = \frac{\epsilon_0(x)}{\sqrt{1 - \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3}} \geq \epsilon_0(x)$, with a condition, given

by: $\left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 < 1$

$$E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{go}(x) = E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{do(ao)}(x) = -E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 \leq 0, \quad (8.b)$$

corresponding to the decrease in both $E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, for a given x .

C. Effect of Temperature T, with Given x and $r_{d(a)}$

Here, the intrinsic band gap $E_{\text{gin(gip)}}(r_{d(a)}, x, T)$ at any T is given by (Van Cong, 2023; Gürbulak, 2021; Yamamoto, 2001):

$$E_{\text{gin(gip)}}(r_{d(a)}, x, T) \text{ in eV} = E_{\text{gn(gp)}}(r_{d(a)}, x) - 10^{-4} \times T^2 \times \left[\frac{7.205 \times x}{T+94 \text{ K}} + \frac{5.405 \times (1-x)}{T+204 \text{ K}} \right], \quad (9)$$

which gives: $E_{\text{gin(gip)}}(r_{\text{do(ao)}}, x = 0, T = 0\text{K}) = 1.52 \text{ eV}$ and $E_{\text{gin(gip)}}(r_{\text{do(ao)}}, x = 1, T = 0\text{K}) \simeq 1.80 \text{ eV}$, and $E_{\text{gin(gip)}}(r_{\text{do(ao)}}, x = 0, T = 300 \text{ K}) \simeq 1.42 \text{ eV}$ and $E_{\text{gin(gip)}}(r_{\text{do(ao)}}, x = 1, T = 300 \text{ K}) \simeq 1.63 \text{ eV}$,

suggesting that, for given x and $r_{d(a)}$, $E_{\text{gin(gip)}}$ decreases with an increasing T.

Furthermore, in the n(p)-type X(x)-alloy, one can define the intrinsic carrier concentration $n_{\text{in(ip)}}$ by:

$$n_{\text{in(p)}}^2(T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv N_c(T, x) \times N_v(T, x) \times \exp\left(\frac{-E_{\text{gin(p)}}(T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{k_B T}\right), \quad (10)$$

where $N_{c(v)}(T, x)$ is the conduction (valence)-band density of states, being defined as:

$$N_{c(v)}(T, x) = 2 \times \left(\frac{m_{c(v)}(x) \times k_B T}{2\pi\hbar^2}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \text{ (cm}^{-3}\text{)}. \quad (11)$$

So, the numerical results of $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, $B_{\text{do(ao)}}(x)$, $\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and $E_{\text{gin(gip)}}(r_{d(a)}, x, T)$, calculated using Equations 4, 5, 8a (8b) and 9, are reported in following Table 1.

Table 1 in Appendix 1.

D. Heavy Doping Effect, with Given T, x and $r_{d(a)}$

Here, as given in our previous works (Van Cong, 2023; Van Cong & Debiais, 1993), the Fermi energy $E_{Fn}(-E_{Fp})$, band gap narrowing (BGN), and apparent band gap narrowing (ABGN), are reported in the following.

First, the Fermi energy $E_{Fn}(-E_{Fp})$, obtained for any T and any d(a)-density, $N_{d(a)}$, being investigated in our previous paper [3], with a precision of the order of 2.11×10^{-4} , is found to be given by (Van Cong & Debiais, 1993):

$$\frac{E_{Fn}(u)}{k_B T} \left(\frac{-E_{Fp}(u)}{k_B T}\right) = \frac{G(u) + Au^B F(u)}{1 + Au^B}, \quad A = 0.0005372 \text{ and } B = 4.82842262, \quad (12)$$

where u is the reduced electron density, $u(N_{d(a)}, T, x) \equiv \frac{N_{d(a)}}{N_{c(v)}(T, x)}$, $F(u) = au^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(1 + bu^{-\frac{4}{3}} + cu^{-\frac{8}{3}}\right)^{-\frac{2}{3}}$, $a = [(3\sqrt{\pi}/4) \times u]^{2/3}$, $b = \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{\pi}{a}\right)^2$, $c = \frac{62.3739855}{1920} \left(\frac{\pi}{a}\right)^4$, and $G(u) \simeq \ln(u) + 2^{-\frac{3}{2}} \times u \times e^{-du}$; $d = 2^{3/2} \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{27}} - \frac{3}{16}\right] > 0$.

Here, one notes that: (i) as $u \gg 1$, according to the HD [d(a)- X(x)- alloy] ER-case, or to the degenerate case, Eq. (12) is reduced to the function $F(u)$, and (ii) $\frac{E_{Fn}(u \ll 1)}{k_B T} \left(\frac{-E_{Fp}(u \ll 1)}{k_B T}\right) \ll -1$, to the LD [a(d)- CdS_{1-x}Se_x- alloy] BR-case, or to the non-degenerate case, Eq. (12) is reduced to the function $G(u)$.

Secondly, if denoting the effective Wigner-Seitz radius $r_{sn(sp)}$, characteristic of the interactions, by:

$$r_{sn(sp)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, x) = 1.1723 \times 10^8 \times \left(\frac{g_{c(v)}}{N_{d(a)}}\right)^{1/3} \times \frac{m_{c(v)}(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)}, g_{c(v)} = 1(1), \quad (13)$$

the correlation energy of an effective electron gas, $E_{cn(cp)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, x)$, is given as [4]:

$$E_{cn(cp)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, x) = \frac{-0.87553}{0.0908+r_{sn(sp)}} + \frac{0.87553}{0.0908+r_{sn(sp)}} + \frac{(2[1-\ln(2)]) \times \ln(r_{sn(sp)}) - 0.093288}{1+0.03847728 \times r_{sn(sp)}^{1.67378876}}.$$

Now, taking into account various spin-polarized chemical potential-energy contributions such as [4]: exchange energy of an effective electron (hole) gas, majority-carrier correlation energy of an effective electron (hole) gas, minority hole (electron) correlation energy, majority electron (hole)-ionized d(a) interaction screened Coulomb potential energy, and finally minority hole (electron)-ionized d(a) interaction screened Coulomb potential energy, the band gap narrowing (BGN) are given as follows.

Then, in the n-type HD X(x)- alloy, the BGN is found to be given by (Van Cong, 2023):

$$\Delta E_{gn}(N_d, r_d, x) \simeq a_1 \times \frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_d, x)} \times N_r^{1/3} + a_2 \times \frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_d, x)} \times N_r^{1/3} \times (2.503 \times [-E_{cn}(r_{sn}) \times r_{sn}]) + a_3 \times \left[\frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_d, x)}\right]^{5/4} \times \sqrt{\frac{m_v}{m_c}} \times N_r^{1/4} + a_4 \times \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_d, x)}} \times N_r^{1/2} \times 2 + a_5 \times \left[\frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_d, x)}\right]^{3/2} \times N_r^{1/6}, \quad N_r \equiv \left(\frac{N_d}{9.999 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}}\right), \quad (14n)$$

where $a_1 = 3.8 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$, $a_2 = 6.5 \times 10^{-4}(\text{eV})$, $a_3 = 2.8 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$, $a_4 = 5.597 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$ and $a_5 = 8.1 \times 10^{-4}(\text{eV})$, and in the p-type HD X(x)- alloy, as:

$$\Delta E_{gp}(N_a, r_a, x) \simeq a_1 \times \frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_a, x)} \times N_r^{1/3} + a_2 \times \frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_a, x)} \times N_r^{1/3} \times (2.503 \times [-E_{cp}(r_{sp}) \times r_{sp}]) + a_3 \times \left[\frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_a, x)}\right]^{5/4} \times \sqrt{\frac{m_c}{m_v}} \times N_r^{1/4} + 2a_4 \times \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_a, x)}} \times N_r^{1/2} + a_5 \times \left[\frac{\varepsilon_0(x)}{\varepsilon(r_a, x)}\right]^{3/2} \times N_r^{1/6}, \quad N_r \equiv \left(\frac{N_a}{9.999 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}}\right), \quad (14p)$$

where $a_1 = 3.15 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$, $a_2 = 5.41 \times 10^{-4}(\text{eV})$, $a_3 = 2.32 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$, $a_4 = 4.12 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$ and $a_5 = 9.80 \times 10^{-5}(\text{eV})$.

Therefore, in the HD[d(a)- X(x)- alloy] ER, we can define the effective extrinsic carrier concentration, $n_{en(ep)}^*$, by:

$$n_{en(ep)}^*(N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \sqrt{N_{d(a)} \times p_o(n_o)} = n_{in(ip)}(T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times \exp\left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(aggp)}}{2k_B T}\right], \quad (15)$$

where the apparent band gap narrowing (ABGN), $\Delta E_{agn(aggp)}$, is defined by:

$$\Delta E_{agn}(N_d, T, r_d, x) \equiv \Delta E_{gn}(N_d, r_d, x) + k_B T \times \ln\left(\frac{N_d}{N_c(T, x)}\right) - E_{Fn}(N_d, T, x), \quad (16n)$$

$$\Delta E_{aggp}(N_a, T, r_a, x) \equiv \Delta E_{gp}(N_a, r_a, x) + k_B T \times \ln\left(\frac{N_a}{N_v(T, x)}\right) + E_{Fp}(N_a, T, x). \quad (16p)$$

Total Minority-Carrier Saturation Current Density

In the two $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ X(x)- alloy -junction solar cells, denoted respectively by I(II), the total carrier-minority saturation current density is defined by:

$$J_{oI(oII)} \equiv J_{Eno(Epo)} + J_{Bpo(Bno)} \quad (17)$$

where $J_{Bpo(Bno)}$ is the minority-electron (hole) saturation current density injected into the LD[a(d)- X(x)- alloy] BR, and $J_{Eno(Epo)}$ is the minority-hole (electron) saturation-current density injected into the HD[d(a)- X(x)- alloy] ER.

$J_{Bpo(Bno)}$ in the LD[a(d)- X(x)- alloy]BR

Here, $J_{Bpo(Bno)}$ is determined by (Van Cong, 2023):

$$J_{Bpo(Bno)}(N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x) = \frac{e \times n_{ip(in)}^2(T, r_{a(d)}, x) \times \sqrt{\frac{D_{e(h)}(N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x)}{\tau_{eB(hB)}(N_{a(d)})}}}{N_{a(d)}}, \quad (18)$$

where $n_{ip(in)}^2(T, r_{a(d)}, x)$ is determined Eq. (10), $D_{e(h)}(N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x)$ is the minority electron (minority hole) diffusion coefficient:

$$D_e(N_a, T, r_a, x) = \frac{k_B T}{e} \times \left[200 + \frac{8300}{1 + \left(\frac{N_a}{1.3 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}}\right)^{0.91}} \right] \times \left(\frac{\varepsilon(r_a, x)}{\varepsilon_0(x)}\right)^2 \text{ (cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)}, \quad (19a)$$

$$D_h(N_d, T, r_d, x) = \frac{k_B T}{e} \times \left[130 + \frac{270}{1 + \left(\frac{N_d}{8 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}}\right)^{1.25}} \right] \times \left(\frac{\varepsilon(r_d, x)}{\varepsilon_0(x)}\right)^2 \text{ (cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)}, \quad (19b)$$

and $\tau_{eB(hB)}(N_{d(a)})$ is the minority electron (minority hole) lifetime in the BR:

$$\tau_{eB}(N_a)^{-1} = \frac{1}{10^{-7}} + 3 \times 10^{-13} \times N_a + 1.83 \times 10^{-31} \times N_a^2, \quad (20a)$$

$$\tau_{hB}(N_d)^{-1} = \frac{1}{10^{-7}} + 11.76 \times 10^{-13} \times N_d + 2.78 \times 10^{-31} \times N_d^2. \quad (20b)$$

***J*_{Eno(Epo)} in the HD[d(a)- X(x)- alloy]ER**

In the non-uniformly and heavily doped emitter region of d(a)- X(x) devices, the effective Gaussian d(a)-density profile or the d(a) (majority-e(h)) density, is defined in such the HD[d(a)- X(x) alloy] ER-width W, as (Van Cong, 2023):

$$\rho_{d(a)}(y, N_{d(a)}, W) = N_{d(a)} \times \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{y}{W}\right)^2 \times \ln\left[\frac{N_{d(a)}}{N_{do(ao)}(W)}\right]\right\} \equiv N_{d(a)} \times \left[\frac{N_{d(a)}}{N_{do(ao)}(W)}\right]^{-\left(\frac{y}{W}\right)^2}, \quad 0 \leq y \leq W,$$

$$N_{do(ao)}(W) \equiv 7.9 \times 10^{17} (2 \times 10^5) \times \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{W}{184.2 (1) \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}}\right)^{1.066 (0.5)}\right\} (\text{cm}^{-3}), \quad (21)$$

where $\rho_{d(a)}(y=0) = N_{d(a)}$ is the surface d(a)-density, and at the emitter-base junction, $\rho_{d(a)}(y=W) = N_{do(ao)}(W)$, which decreases with increasing W. Further, the “effective doping density” is defined by:

$$N_{d(a)}^*(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \rho_{d(a)}(y) / \exp\left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(agg)}(\rho_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{k_B T}\right],$$

$$N_{d(a)}^*(y=0, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \frac{N_{d(a)}}{\exp\left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(agg)}(N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{k_B T}\right]}, \text{ and}$$

$$N_{d(a)}^*(y=W, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \frac{N_{do(ao)}(W)}{\exp\left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(agg)}(N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{k_B T}\right]}, \quad (22)$$

where the apparent band gap narrowing $\Delta E_{agn(agg)}$ is determined in Eq. (16), replacing $N_{d(a)}$ by $\rho_{d(a)}(y, N_{d(a)}, W)$.

Now, we can define the minority hole (minority electron) transport parameter $F_{h(e)}$ as:

$$F_{h(e)}(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \frac{n_{in(ip)}^2(T, r_{d(a)})}{p_o(n_o) \times D_{h(e)}} = \frac{N_{d(a)}^*}{D_{h(e)}} \equiv \frac{N_{d(a)}}{D_{h(e)}} \times \left(\frac{n_{in(ip)}}{n_{in(ip)}^*}\right)^2 \equiv \frac{N_{d(a)}}{D_{h(e)} \times \exp\left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(agg)}}{k_B T}\right]} (\text{cm}^{-5} \times \text{s}), \quad (23)$$

the minority hole (electron) diffusion length, $L_{h(e)}(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x)$ by:

$$L_{h(e)}^{-2}(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) = [\tau_{hE(eE)} \times D_{h(e)}]^{-1} = (C \times F_{h(e)})^2 = \left(C \times \frac{N_{d(a)}^*}{D_{h(e)}}\right)^2 = \left(C \times \frac{n_{in(ip)}^2(T, r_{d(a)})}{p_o(n_o) \times D_{h(e)}}\right)^2,$$

where the constant C was chosen to be equal to: $2.0893 \times 10^{-30} (cm^4/s)$, and the minority hole (minority electron) lifetime $\tau_{hE(eE)}$ as:

$$\tau_{hE(eE)} \equiv \frac{1}{D_{h(e)} \times L_{h(e)}^{-2}} = \frac{1}{D_{h(e)} \times (C \times F_{h(e)})^2}. \quad (24)$$

Then, under low-level injection, in the absence of external generation, and for the steady-state case, we can define the minority-h(e) density by:

$$p_o(y)[n_o(y)] \equiv \frac{n_{in(ip)}^2}{N_{d(a)}^*(y=W, T, r_{d(a)}, x)}, \quad (25)$$

and a normalized excess minority-h(e) density $u(x)$ or a relative deviation between $p(y)[n(y)]$ and $p_o(y)[n_o(y)]$.

$$u(y) \equiv \frac{p(y)[n(y)] - p_o(y)[n_o(y)]}{p_o(y)[n_o(y)]}, \quad (26)$$

which must verify the two following boundary conditions as:

$$u(y=0) \equiv \frac{-J_h(y=0)[J_e(y=0)]}{eS \times p_o(y=0)[n_o(y=0)]},$$

$$u(y=W) = \exp\left(\frac{V}{n_{I(I)}(V) \times V_T}\right) - 1.$$

Here, $n_{I(I)}(V)$ is the photovoltaic conversion factor, being determined later, $S \left(\frac{cm}{s}\right)$ is the surface recombination velocity at the emitter contact, V is the applied voltage, $V_T \equiv (k_B T/e)$ is the thermal voltage, and the minority-hole (electron) current density $J_{h(e)}(y, r_{d(a)}, x)$.

Further, from the Fick's law for minority hole (electron)-diffusion equations, one has (Van Cong, 2023):

$$J_{h(e)}(y, r_{d(a)}, x) = \frac{-e(+e) \times n_{in(ip)}^2}{F_{h(e)}(y)} \times \frac{du(y)}{dy} = \frac{-e(+e)n_{in(ip)}^2 D_{h(e)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, x)}{N_{d(a)}^*(y, r_{d(a)}, x)} \times \frac{du(y)}{dy}, \quad (27)$$

where $N_{d(a)}^*(y, r_{d(a)}, x)$ is given in Eq. (22), $D_{h(e)}$ and $F_{h(e)}$ are determined respectively in Equations (19) and (23), and from the minority-hole (electron) continuity equation as:

$$\frac{dJ_{h(e)}(y, r_{d(a)}, x)}{dy} = -e(+e) \times n_i^2 n(p) \times \frac{u(y)}{F_{h(e)}(y) \times L_{h(e)}^2(y)} = -e(+e) \times n_i^2 n(p) \times \frac{u(y)}{N_{d(a)}^*(y, r_{d(a)}, x) \times \tau_{hE}(eE)}, \quad (28)$$

Therefore, the following second-order differential equation is obtained:

$$\frac{d^2u(y)}{dy^2} - \frac{dF_{h(e)}(y)}{dy} \times \frac{du(y)}{dy} - \frac{u(y)}{L_{h(e)}^2(y)} = 0, \quad (29)$$

Then, taking into account the two above boundary conditions given in Eq. (22), one thus gets the general solution of this Eq. (29), as:

$$u(y) = \frac{\sinh(P(y)) + I(W, S) \times \cosh(P(y))}{\sinh(P(W)) + I(W, S) \times \cosh(P(W))} \times \left(\exp\left(\frac{V}{n_{I(II)}(V) \times V_T}\right) - 1 \right), \quad (30)$$

where the factor $I(W, S)$ is determined by: $D_{h(e)}(N_d, T, r_{d(a)}, x)$

$$I(T, r_{d(a)}, x, W, S) = \frac{D_{h(e)}(y=W, N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{S \times L_{h(e)}(y=W, N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)}. \quad (31)$$

Further, since $\frac{dP(y)}{dy} \equiv C \times F_{h(e)}(y) = \frac{1}{L_{h(e)}(x)}$, $C = 2.0893 \times 10^{-30}$ (cm^4/s), for the X(x)-alloy, being an empirical parameter, chosen for each crystalline semiconductor, $P(y)$ is thus found to be defined by:

$$\frac{P(y)}{W} \equiv \int_0^y \frac{dy}{L_{h(e)}(y)}, \quad 0 \leq y \leq W, \quad P(y=W) \equiv \left(\frac{1}{W} \times \int_0^W \frac{dy}{L_{h(e)}(y)}\right) \times W \equiv \frac{W}{L_{h(e)}^*(y)} = \frac{L_{h(e)}(y)}{L_{h(e)}^*(y)} \times \frac{W}{L_{h(e)}(y)}, \quad (32)$$

where $L_{h(e)}^*(y)$ is the effective minority hole (minority electron) diffusion length. Further, the minority-hole (electron) current density injected into the HD[d(a)- X(x) alloy] ER is found to be given by:

$$J_{h(e)}(y, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S, V) = -J_{Eno}(y, W, N_d, T, r_d, x, S) [J_{Epo}(y, W, N_a, T, r_a, x, S)] \times \left(\exp\left(\frac{V}{n_{I(II)}(V) \times V_T}\right) - 1 \right), \quad (33)$$

where $J_{Eno}(Epo)$ is the saturation minority hole (minority electron) current density,

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(y, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S) = \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \frac{\cosh(P(x)) + I(W, S) \times \sinh(P(x))}{\sinh(P(W)) + I(W, S) \times \cosh(P(W))}. \quad (34)$$

In the following, we will denote $P(W)$ and $I(W, S)$ by P and I , for a simplicity. So, Eq. (30) gives:

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(y = 0, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S) = \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \frac{1}{\sinh(P) + I \times \cosh(P)}, \quad (35)$$

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(y = W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S) = \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(y=W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \frac{\cosh(P) + I \times \sinh(P)}{\sinh(P) + I \times \cosh(P)}, \quad (36)$$

and then,

$$\frac{J_{h(e)}(y=0, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S, V)}{J_{h(e)}(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S, V)} \equiv \frac{J_{Eno(Epo)}(y=0, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)}{J_{Eno(Epo)}(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)} = \frac{1}{\cosh(P) + I \times \sinh(P)}. \quad (37)$$

Now, if defining the effective excess minority-hole (electron) charge storage in the emitter region by:

$$Q_{h(e)}^*(y = W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \int_0^W +e(-e) \times u(y) \times p_o(y) [n_o(y)] \times \frac{\tau_{hE(eE)}(N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{\tau_{hE(eE)}(\rho_{d(a)}(x), T, r_{d(a)}, x)} dy,$$

and the effective minority hole (minority electron) transit time $[htt(ett)]$ by: $\tau_{htt(ett)}^*(y = W, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, x, S) \equiv Q_{h(e)}^*(y = W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) / J_{Eno(Epo)}(y = W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)$, and from Equations (24, 31), one obtains:

$$\frac{\tau_{htt(ett)}^*(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)}{\tau_{hE(eE)}} \equiv 1 - \frac{J_{Eno(Epo)}(y=0, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)}{J_{Eno(Epo)}(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)} = 1 - \frac{1}{\cosh(P) + I \times \sinh(P)}. \quad (38)$$

Now, some important results can be obtained and discussed below.

As $P \ll 1$ (or $W \ll L_{h(e)}$) and $S \rightarrow \infty$, $I \equiv I(W, S) = \frac{D_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{S \times L_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)} \rightarrow 0$, from Eq. (38),

one has: $\frac{\tau_{htt(ett)}^*(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)}{\tau_{hE(eE)}} \rightarrow 0$, suggesting a completely transparent emitter region (CTER)-case, where, from Eq. (36), one obtains:

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(y = W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(y=W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \frac{1}{P(W)}. \quad (39)$$

Further, as $P \gg 1$ (or $W \gg L_{h(e)}$) and $S \rightarrow 0$, $I \equiv I(y = W, r_{d(a)}, x, S) = \frac{D_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{S \times L_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)} \rightarrow \infty$, and from Eq. (38) one has: $\frac{\tau_{htt(ett)}^*(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)}{\tau_{hE(eE)}} \rightarrow 1$, suggesting a completely opaque emitter region (COER)-case, where, from Eq. (36), one gets:

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(y = W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S \rightarrow 0) \rightarrow \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(y=W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \tanh(P). \quad (40)$$

In summary, in the two $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ X(x)-alloy junction solar cells, the dark carrier-minority saturation current density $J_{oI(oII)}$, defined in Eq. (17), is now rewritten as:

$$J_{oI(oII)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}, x) \equiv J_{Eno(Epo)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S) + J_{Bpo(Bno)}(N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x), \quad (41)$$

where $J_{Eno(Epo)}$ and $J_{Bpo(Bno)}$ are determined respectively in Equations (36, 18).

Photovoltaic Conversion Effect at 300K

Here, in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ X(x) -alloy junction solar cells at $T=300$ K, denoted respectively by I(II), and for physical conditions, respectively, as:

$$W = 15 \mu\text{m}, N_{d(a)} = 10^{19} \text{cm}^{-3} (10^{20} \text{cm}^{-3}), r_{d(a)}, x, S = 100 \left(\frac{\text{cm}}{\text{s}}\right); N_{a(d)} = 10^{17} \text{cm}^{-3}, r_{a(d)}, x, \quad (42)$$

we propose, at given open circuit voltages: $V_{ocI1(ocI2)}$ and $V_{ocII1(ocII2)}$, the corresponding data of the short circuit current density $J_{scI(II)}$, in order to formulate our following treatment method of two fix points (Green, 2022; Moon et al., 2016), as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{at } V_{ocI1(ocI2)}(V) = 0.980 (1.1272), J_{scI1(scI2)}(\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2) = 27.06 (29.76), \\ \text{at } V_{ocII1(ocII2)}(V) = 0.980 (1.03), J_{scII1(scII2)}(\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2) = 24.2 (29.84). \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

Now, we define the net current density J at $T=300$ K, obtained for the infinite shunt resistance, and expressed as a function of the applied voltage V , flowing through the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ X(x)-alloy junction of solar cells, as:

$$J(V) \equiv J_{ph.}(V) - J_{oI(oII)} \times (e^{X_{I(II)}(V)} - 1), X_{I(II)}(V) \equiv \frac{V}{n_{I(II)}(V) \times V_T}, V_T \equiv \frac{k_B T}{e} = 0.02585 \text{ V}, \quad (44)$$

where the function $n_{I(II)}(V)$ is the photovoltaic conversion factor (PVCF), noting that as $V = V_{oc}$, being the open circuit voltage, $J(V = V_{oc}) = 0$, the photocurrent density is defined by: $J_{ph}(V = V_{oc}) \equiv J_{scI(scII)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc})$, for $V_{oc} \geq V_{ocI1(ocII1)}$.

Therefore, the photovoltaic conversion effect occurs, according to:

$$J_{scI(scII)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc}) \equiv J_{oI(oII)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x) \times (e^{X_{I(II)}(V_{oc})} - 1), \quad (45)$$

where $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) \equiv n_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc})$, and $X_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) \equiv \frac{V_{oc}}{n_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) \times V_T}$.

Here, one remarks that (i) for a given V_{oc} , both $n_{I(II)}$ and $J_{oI(oII)}$ have the same variations, obtained in the same physical conditions, as observed in the following calculation, (ii) the function $(e^{X_{I(II)}(V_{oc})} - 1)$ or the PVCF, $n_{I(II)}$, representing the photovoltaic conversion effect, converts the light, represented by $J_{scI(scII)}$, into the electricity, by $J_{oI(oII)}$, and finally, for given $(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc})$ -values, $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc})$ is determined.

Now, for $V_{oc} \geq V_{ocI1(ocII1)}$, one can propose the general expressions for the PVCF, in order to get exactly the values of $n_{I1(II1)}(V_{ocI1(ocII1)})$ and $n_{I2(II2)}(V_{ocI2(ocII2)})$, as functions of V_{oc} , by:

$$n_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc}) = n_{I1(II1)}(V_{ocI1(ocII1)}) + n_{I2(II2)}(V_{ocI2(ocII2)}) \times \left(\frac{V_{oc}}{V_{ocI1(ocII1)}} - 1 \right)^{\alpha(\beta)}, \quad (46)$$

where, for example, the values of $\alpha(\beta)$, obtained for $x = (0, 0.5 \text{ and } 1)$, will be reported in Tables 3 and 5, for $[X(x) \equiv \text{GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x]$ alloy junctions.

So, one can determine the general expressions for the fill factors, as:

$$F_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc}) = \frac{X_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) - \ln[X_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) + b]}{X_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) + a}, \quad a=1 \text{ and } b=0.72. \quad (47)$$

Finally, the efficiency $\eta_{I(II)}$ can be defined in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ $X(x)$ alloy-junction solar cells, by:

$$\eta_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc}) \equiv \frac{J_{scI(scII)} \times V_{oc} \times F_{I(II)}}{P_{in}}, \quad (48)$$

being assumed to be obtained at 1 sun illumination or at AM1.5G spectrum ($P_{in} = 0.100 \frac{W}{cm^2}$).

It should be noted that the maximal values of $\eta_{I(II)}$, $\eta_{I(II)max}$, are obtained at the corresponding ones of $V_{ocI(ocII)}$, at which $\frac{\partial \eta_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, S, N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, V_{oc})}{\partial V_{oc}} = 0$, as those given in next Tables 3 and 5, being marked in bold. Further, from the well-known Carnot's theorem, being obtained by the second principle

in thermodynamics, or by the entropy law, the maximum efficiency of a heat engine operating between hot (**H**) and cold (**C**) reservoirs is the ratio of the temperature difference between the reservoirs, $T_H - T_C$, to the H-reservoir temperature, T_H , expressed as:

$$\eta_{I(II)\max}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, S, N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, V_{oc;\max.}) = 1 - \frac{T_C=300\text{ K}}{T_H(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, S, N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, V_{oc;\max.})}. \quad (49)$$

Numerical Results and Concluding Remarks

We will respectively consider the two following cases of $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ -junctions such as:

HD (Te ; Sb ; Sn) X(x) alloy ER – LD (Mg ; In ; Cd) X(x) – alloy BR –case, according to: 3 (n^+p) – junctions denoted by: (Te^+Mg, Sb^+In, Sn^+Cd) , and

HD (Mg ; In ; Cd) X(x) alloy ER – LD (Te ; Sb ; Sn) X(x) – alloy BR –case, according to: 3 (p^+n) – junctions denoted by: (Mg^+Te, In^+Sb, Cd^+Sn) .

Now, by using the physical conditions, given in Eq. (42), we can determine various following photovoltaic conversion coefficients.

Firs case: HD [Te ; Sb ; Sn] X(x) – Alloy ER – LD [Mg ; In ; Cd] X(x) – Alloy BR

Here, there are the 3 $(n^+p) - X(x)$ junctions, being denoted by: (Te^+Mg, Sb^+In, Sn^+Cd) .

Then, the numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{htt}^*}{\tau_{hE}}$, J_{Bpo} , J_{Eno} and J_{OI} , are calculated using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, and obtained, as those given in Table 2. Further, those of n_I , J_{sclI} , F_I , η_I , and T_H , are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, and reported in the following Table 3.

Tables 2 and 3 in Appendix 1.

Second case: HD [Mg ; In ; Cd] X(x) – Alloy ER – LD [Te ; Sb, Sn] X(x) – Alloy BR

Here, there are 3 $(p^+n) - X(x)$ -junctions, being denoted by: (Mg^+Te, In^+Sb, Cd^+Sn) .

Then, the numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}}$, J_{Bno} , J_{Epo} and J_{OII} , are calculated using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, and obtained, as those given in Table 4. Further, those of n_{II} , J_{sclII} , F_{II} , η_{II} , and T_H , are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, and reported in the following Table 5.

Tables 4 and 5 in Appendix 1

Finally, some concluding remarks are obtained and discussed as follows.

(i)-First, with increasing $x=(0, 0.5, 1)$, from Table 3, obtained for the single $n^+ - p$ $X(x)$ -alloy junction solar cells, and for given $r_{Sn(Cd)}$ -radius, for example, one obtains: $\eta_{I_{max.}(\nearrow)} = 31.14\%$, 31.55% , **32.11%**, according to $T_H(K) = 435.7, 438.3, \mathbf{441.9}$, at $V_{ocI}(V) = 1.07, 1.07, \mathbf{1.06}$, respectively.

(ii)- Secondly, with increasing $x=(0, 0.5, 1)$, from Table 5, obtained for the single $p^+ - n$ $X(x)$ -alloy junction solar cells, and for given $r_{Cd(Sn)}$ -radius, for example, one gets: $\eta_{I_{max.}(\searrow)} = \mathbf{33.04\%}$, 32.65% , 32.51% , according to $T_H(K) = \mathbf{448.0}, 445.4, 444.5$, at $V_{ocII}(V)[> V_{ocI}(V)] = 1.20, 1.19, 1.18$, respectively, suggesting that such $\eta_{I_{max.}(I_{max.})}$ -and- T_H variations depend on $V_{ocII}(V)[> V_{ocI}(V)]$ – values.

Then, as given in Table 3, for $x = 0$ and $r_{d(a)} = r_{Te(Mg)}$, one gets: $\eta_I = 23.48\%$ and 29.71% at $V_{oc} = 0.98\text{ V}$ and 1.1272 V , respectively, which can also be compared with the corresponding results obtained for the single-junction GaAs thin-film solar cell, 22.08% and 29.71% , obtained with relative deviations in absolute values, 6.34% and 2.1% , and given respectively by Moon et al. (2016) and Green et al. (2022).

Finally, one notes that, in order to obtain the highest efficiencies, the single $GaAs_{1-x}Te_x$ -alloy junction solar cells could be chosen rather than the single crystalline GaAs-junction solar cell.

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Appendix 1

Table 1. From Equations (5, 8a, 8b, 9) and in the n(p)-type GaAs_{1-x}Te_x-Alloy, the Numerical Results of the Energy-Band-Structure Parameters, Reported Below, Suggest that, with Increasing x and r_{d(a)}, both B_{do(ao)}(x) and ε(r_{d(a)}, x) Decrease, while the Other Ones Increase

Donor		As	Te	Sb	Sn
r _d (nm)	↗	r_{do}=0.118	0.132	0.136	0.140
x	↗	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1
B _{do} (x) in 10 ⁸ (N/m ²)	↗	1.21, 2.69, 4.37			
ε(r _d , x)	↘	13.1, 12.7, 12.3	12.3, 11.9, 11.5	11.8, 11.5, 11.1	11.3, 11.0, 10.6
E _d (r _d , x) meV	↗	5.21, 11.6, 18.8	5.91, 13.1, 21.3	6.38, 14.2, 23.0	6.99, 15.5, 25.2
E _{gn} (r _d , x) eV	↗	1.52, 1.66, 1.80	1.52, 1.66, 1.80	1.52, 1.66, 1.80	1.52, 1.66, 1.80
E _{gin} (T = 300K, r _d , x) eV	↗	1.42, 1.53, 1.63	1.42, 1.53, 1.63	1.42, 1.53, 1.63	1.42, 1.53, 1.63
Acceptor		Ga	Mg	In	Cd
r _a (nm)	↗	r_{ao}=0.126	0.140	0.144	0.148
x	↗	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1
B _{ao} (x) in 10 ⁸ (N/m ²)	↗	4.39, 7.16, 10.3			
ε(r _a , x)	↘	13.1, 12.7, 12.3	12.4, 12.0, 11.6	12.0, 11.6, 11.2	11.5, 11.1, 10.8
E _a (r _a , x) meV	↗	23.0, 37.5, 53.9	25.7, 41.9, 60.3	27.5, 44.9, 64.6	29.8, 48.7, 70.1
E _{gp} (r _a , x) eV	↗	1.52, 1.66, 1.80	1.52, 1.66, 1.80	1.52, 1.66, 1.81	1.53, 1.67, 1.81
E _{gip} (T = 300K, r _a , x) eV	↗	1.42, 1.53, 1.63	1.43, 1.53, 1.64	1.43, 1.53, 1.64	1.43, 1.54, 1.65

Table 2. In the HD [(Te; Sb; Sn)- GaAs_{1-x}Te_x-alloy] ER-LD[(Mg; In; Cd)-GaAs_{1-x}Te_x-Alloy] BR, for Physical Conditions Given in Eq. (42) and for a Given x, our Numerical Results of $\frac{\tau_{htt}^*}{\tau_{hE}}$, J_{Bpo} , J_{Eno} and J_{ol} , are Computed, Using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), Respectively, Noting that J_{ol} Decreases Slightly with Increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -Radius for Given x, but it Increases Strongly with Increasing x for Given $r_{d(a)}$ -Radius, Being New Results

n^+p		Te^+Mg	Sb^+In	Sn^+Cd
Here, $\mathbf{x=0}$, and for the (Te^+Mg, Sb^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions and from Eq. (34), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{htt}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition.				
J_{Bpo} in 10^{-19} (A/cm^2)	↘	1.0315	0.9965	0.9565
J_{Eno} in 10^{-23} (A/cm^2)	↘	1.7830	1.7258	1.6624
J_{ol} in 10^{-19} (A/cm^2)	↘	1.0317	0.9967	0.9567
Here, $\mathbf{x=0.5}$, and for the (Te^+Mg, Sb^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions and from Eq. (34), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{htt}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition.				
J_{Bpo} in 10^{-21} (A/cm^2)	↘	9.6802	9.3518	8.9764
J_{Eno} in 10^{-23} (A/cm^2)	↘	5.6647	5.3319	4.9564
J_{ol} in 10^{-21} (A/cm^2)	↘	9.7369	9.4051	9.0260
Here, $\mathbf{x=1}$, and for the (Te^+Mg, Sb^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions and from Eq. (34), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{htt}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition.				
J_{Bpo} in 10^{-21} (A/cm^2)	↘	9.6802	9.3518	8.9764
J_{Eno} in 10^{-23} (A/cm^2)	↘	5.6647	5.3319	4.9564
J_{ol} in 10^{-21} (A/cm^2)	↘	9.7369	9.4051	9.0260
Here, $\mathbf{x=1}$, and for the (Te^+Mg, Sb^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions and from Eq. (34), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{htt}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition.				
J_{Bpo} in 10^{-22} (A/cm^2)	↘	4.6184	4.4617	4.2826
J_{Eno} in 10^{-24} (A/cm^2)	↘	8.6519	7.9136	7.0919
J_{ol} in 10^{-22} (A/cm^2)	↘	4.7049	4.5408	4.3535

Table 3. In the HD [(Te; Sb; Sn)- GaAs_{1-x}Te_x-alloy] ER-LD[(Mg; In; Cd)-GaAs_{1-x}Te_x-alloy] BR, for Physical Conditions Given in Eq. (42) and for a Given x, Our Numerical Results of n_I , J_{sci} , F_I , η_I , and T_H , are Computed, Using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), Respectively, Noting that Both $\eta_{I_{max}}$ and T_H , Marked in Bold, Increase with Increasing x for Given $r_{d(a)}$, Being New Results

$V_{oc}(V)$	n_I	$J_{sci}(\frac{mA}{cm^2})$	$F_I(\%)$	$\eta_I(\%)$
Here, $x=0$. For the (Te^+Mg, Sb^+In, Sn^+Cd) junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is 1.0822.				
n^+p	$Te^+Mg; Sb^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+Mg; Sb^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+Mg; Sb^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+Mg; Sb^+In; Sn^+Cd$
0.980	0.945; 0.944; 0.943	27.06; 27.06; 27.06	88.54; 88.55; 88.56	23.48; 23.48; 23.48
1.06	1.017; 1.016; 1.015	33.09; 33.09; 33.10	88.59; 88.59; 88.60	31.07; 31.08; 31.09
1.07	1.027; 1.026; 1.025	32.83; 32.84; 32.84	88.59; 88.59; 88.60	31.12; 31.13; 31.14
			$V_{ocI} = 1.07 V$	435.5; 435.6; 435.7=$T_H(K)$
1.08	1.037; 1.036; 1.035	32.47; 32.47; 32.48	88.58; 88.59; 88.60	31.06; 31.07; 31.08
1.1272	1.084; 1.083; 1.082	29.76; 29.76; 29.76	88.56; 88.57; 88.58	29.71; 29.71; 29.72
3	3.317; 3.314; 3.311	0.160; 0.160; 0.159	87.28; 87.29; 87.30	0.420; 0.418; 0.416
Here, $x=0.5$. For the (Te^+Mg, Sb^+In, Sn^+Cd) junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is 1.0818				
n^+p	$Te^+Mg; Sb^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+Mg; Sb^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+Mg; Sb^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+Mg; Sb^+In; Sn^+Cd$
0.980	0.892; 0.892; 0.891	27.06; 27.06; 27.06	89.04; 89.04; 88.05	23.61; 23.61; 23.61
1.06	0.961; 0.960; 0.959	33.37; 33.37; 33.38	89.08; 89.08; 89.09	31.51; 31.51; 31.52
1.07	0.970; 0.969; 0.968	33.08; 33.09; 33.09	89.08; 89.08; 89.09	31.53; 31.54; 31.55
			$V_{ocI} = 1.07 V$	438.1; 438.2; 438.3=$T_H(K)$
1.08	0.979; 0.978; 0.977	32.69; 32.69; 32.70	89.07; 89.08; 89.09	31.44; 31.45; 31.46
1.1272	1.024; 1.023; 1.022	29.78; 29.78; 29.78	89.05; 89.06; 89.07	29.89; 29.90; 29.90
3	3.132; 3.130; 3.127	0.119; 0.118; 0.118	87.82; 87.83; 87.84	0.314; 0.312; 0.311
Here, $x=1$. For the (Te^+Mg, Sb^+In, Sn^+Cd) junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is 1.0815				
n^+p	$Te^+Mg; Sb^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+Mg; Sb^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+Mg; Sb^+In; Sn^+Cd$	$Te^+Mg; Sb^+In; Sn^+Cd$
0.980	0.833; 0.832; 0.831	27.06; 27.06; 27.06	89.60; 89.61; 89.62	23.76; 23.76; 23.76
1.06	0.888; 0.887; 0.887	33.94; 33.95; 33.95	89.64; 89.65; 89.66	31.94; 31.96; 31.97
1.07	0.897; 0.896; 0.895	33.77; 33.78; 33.78	89.64; 89.65; 89.66	32.09; 32.10; 32.11
			$V_{ocI} = 1.06 V$	441.8; 441.8; 441.9=$T_H(K)$
1.08	0.905; 0.904; 0.903	33.45; 33.46; 33.47	89.64; 89.65; 89.66	32.08; 32.09; 32.11
1.1272	0.956; 0.955; 0.954	29.86; 29.86; 29.86	89.62; 89.63; 89.64	30.16; 30.16; 30.17
3	2.924; 2.921; 2.919	0.081; 0.081; 0.080	88.45; 88.46; 88.46	0.215; 0.214; 0.213

Table 4. In the HD [(Mg; In; Cd)-GaAs_{1-x}Te_x-alloy] ER-LD[(Te; Sb; Sn)-GaAs_{1-x}Te_x-alloy] BR, for Physical Conditions Given in Eq. (42) and for a Given x, Our Numerical Results of $\frac{\tau_{eE}^{*}}{\tau_{eE}}$, J_{Bno} , J_{Epo} , and J_{oII} are Computed, Using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), Respectively, Noting that J_{oII} Decreases Slightly with Increasing $r_{a(d)}$ -Radius for Given x, but it Increases Strongly with Increasing x for Given $r_{a(d)}$ -Radius, Being New Results

p^+n		Mg^+Te	In^+Sb	Cd^+Snvvv
Here, $\mathbf{x=0}$, and for the (Mg^+Te, In^+Sb, Cd^+Sn) -junctions and from Eq. (34), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{eE}^{*}}{\tau_{eE}} = (0, 0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition.				
J_{Bno} in 10^{-20} (A/cm^2)	↘	3.0094	2.8418	2.6512
J_{Epo} in 10^{-23} (A/cm^2)	↘	1.1965	1.1298	1.0513
J_{oII} in 10^{-20} (A/cm^2)	↘	3.0106	2.8429	2.6522
Here, $\mathbf{x=0.5}$, and for the (Mg^+Te, In^+Sb, Cd^+Sn) -junctions and from Eq. (34), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{eE}^{*}}{\tau_{eE}} = (0, 0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition.				
J_{Bno} in 10^{-21} (A/cm^2)	↘	2.9734	2.7451	2.4880
J_{Epo} in 10^{-23} (A/cm^2)	↘	1.5138	1.3634	1.1941
J_{oII} in 10^{-21} (A/cm^2)	↘	2.9885	2.7588	2.500
Here, $\mathbf{x=1}$, and for the (Mg^+Te, In^+Sb, Cd^+Sn) -junctions and from Eq. (34), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{eE}^{*}}{\tau_{eE}} = (0, 0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition.				
J_{Bno} in 10^{-22} (A/cm^2)	↘	1.5039	1.3534	1.1870
J_{Epo} in 10^{-24} (A/cm^2)	↘	2.1632	1.8481	1.5130
J_{oII} in 10^{-22} (A/cm^2)	↘	1.5255	1.3719	1.2022

Table 5. In the HD [(Mg; In; Cd)-GaAs_{1-x}Te_x-alloy] ER-LD[(Te; Sb; Sn)-GaAs_{1-x}Te_x-alloy] BR, for Physical Conditions Given in Eq. (42) and for a Given x, Our Numerical Results of n_{II} , J_{scII} , F_{II} , η_{II} , and T_H , are Computed, Using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), Respectively, Noting that Both η_{IImax} . and T_H , Marked in Bold, Decrease with Increasing x for Given $r_{a(d)}$, Being New Results

$V_{oc}(V)$	n_{II}	$J_{scII}(\frac{mA}{cm^2})$	$F_{II}(\%)$	$\eta_{II}(\%)$
Here, $x=0$. For the (Mg ⁺ Te, In ⁺ Sb, Cd ⁺ Sn)-junctions, the value of β given in Eq. (46) is 1.052.				
p^+n	Mg ⁺ Te; In ⁺ Sb; Cd ⁺ Sn	Mg ⁺ Te; In ⁺ Sb; Cd ⁺ Sn	Mg ⁺ Te; In ⁺ Sb; Cd ⁺ Sn	Mg ⁺ Te; In ⁺ Sb; Cd ⁺ Sn
0.980	0.919; 0.918; 0.917	24.20; 24.20; 24.20	88.78; 88.79; 88.81	21.05; 21.06; 21.06
1.03	0.961; 0.960; 0.958	29.84; 29.85; 29.86	88.83; 88.84; 88.85	27.30; 27.31; 27.33
1.19	1.110; 1.108; 1.106	31.21; 31.22; 31.23	88.84; 88.85; 88.86	32.99; 33.01; 33.03
1.20	1.119; 1.117; 1.116	30.96; 30.97; 30.98	88.83; 88.85; 88.86	33.01; 33.02; 33.04
			$V_{ocII} = 1.20 V$	447.8; 447.49; 448.0=$T_H(K)$
1.21	1.129; 1.127; 1.125	30.70; 30.71; 30.72	88.83; 88.84; 88.86	32.99; 33.01; 33.03
3	2.977; 2.973; 2.968	2.545; 2.536; 2.526	88.30; 88.30; 88.32	6.740; 6.719; 6.693
Here, $x=0.5$. For the (Mg ⁺ Te, In ⁺ Sb, Cd ⁺ Sn)-junctions, the value of β given in Eq. (46) is 1.0495.				
p^+n	Mg ⁺ Te; In ⁺ Sb; Cd ⁺ Sn	Mg ⁺ Te; In ⁺ Sb; Cd ⁺ Sn	Mg ⁺ Te; In ⁺ Sb; Cd ⁺ Sn	Mg ⁺ Te; In ⁺ Sb; Cd ⁺ Sn
0.980	0.871; 0.869; 0.867	24.20; 24.20; 24.20	89.24; 89.26; 89.28	21.16; 21.17; 21.17
1.03	0.915; 0.909; 0.907	29.74; 29.76; 29.77	89.28; 89.30; 89.32	27.36; 27.37; 27.39
1.18	1.042; 1.040; 1.038	30.94; 30.95; 30.97	89.29; 89.31; 89.32	32.60; 32.62; 32.64
1.19	1.051; 1.049; 1.047	30.69; 30.71; 30.72	89.29; 89.30; 89.32	32.61; 32.63; 32.65
			$V_{ocII} = 1.19 V$	445.2; 445.3; 445.4=$T_H(K)$
1.20	1.060; 1.058; 1.056	30.43; 30.44; 30.45	89.29; 89.30; 89.32	32.60; 32.62; 32.64
3	2.816; 2.811; 2.805	2.344; 2.333; 2.320	88.79; 88.79; 88.81	6.242; 6.215; 6.182
Here, $x=1$. For the (Mg ⁺ Te, In ⁺ Sb, Cd ⁺ Sn)-junctions, the value of β given in Eq. (46) is 1.0475.				
p^+n	Mg ⁺ Te; In ⁺ Sb; Cd ⁺ Sn	Mg ⁺ Te; In ⁺ Sb; Cd ⁺ Sn	Mg ⁺ Te; In ⁺ Sb; Cd ⁺ Sn	Mg ⁺ Te; In ⁺ Sb; Cd ⁺ Sn
0.980	0.815; 0.813; 0.811	24.20; 24.20; 24.20	89.78; 89.80; 89.82	21.29; 21.30; 21.30
1.03	0.853; 0.851; 0.848	29.79; 29.80; 29.82	89.82; 89.83; 89.86	27.55; 27.57; 27.59
1.17	0.968; 0.966; 0.963	30.88; 30.89; 30.91	89.82; 89.84; 89.86	32.45; 32.47; 32.50
1.18	0.976; 0.974; 0.971	30.63; 30.64; 30.66	89.82; 89.84; 89.86	32.46; 32.49; 32.51
			$V_{ocII} = 1.18 V$	444.2; 444.4; 444.5=$T_H(K)$
1.19	0.985; 0.982; 0.980	30.36; 30.37; 30.39	89.82; 89.84; 89.86	32.45; 32.47; 32.49
3	2.634; 2.628; 2.621	2.069; 2.057; 2.041	89.34; 89.36; 89.38	5.545; 5.513; 5.474